

TACKLING HEALTH INEQUALITIES IN TIMES OF CRISIS

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Summary: The WHO vision of Health for All has not been achieved and a tsunami of determinants are having adverse impacts on health and equity in Europe. This tsunami has been described as a polycrisis with complex and interacting factors. There are reversals in previous gains, a global pandemic, growing inequities, environmental breakdown, wars, financial crises, existential loneliness and social disconnection, and a global refugee crisis. Recently policies and practices centred on inclusion and equity that seemed established have been undermined. This article argues the need for a transformation towards fairer systems that prioritise people and planetary wellbeing over economic growth at all costs.

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Introduction

We are now a quarter of the way through the twenty-first century. In 2000, it was clear that the World Health Organization (WHO) vision of “Health for All by the Year 2000” would not be achieved. However, the extent to which progress would regress in the pursuit of a new goal, such as “Health for All by the Year 2050”, was not yet clear. Since then, a tsunami of social, environmental and commercial determinants of health has had adverse effects on health and equity, both in Europe and globally, threatening the very idea of health for all. This overwhelming confluence of challenges has become known as a “*polycrisis*”.

A polycrisis refers to a scenario in which multiple crises occur simultaneously and interact in complex ways, creating

compounded effects that are more severe than the sum of individual crises.¹ This concept goes beyond the mere coincidence of separate problems, emphasising the interconnectedness and mutual reinforcement of crises across domains such as economic, environmental, social, and political spheres. In a polycrisis, the causal entanglement of these crises makes addressing any single issue in isolation difficult, as attempts to solve one problem may exacerbate others. So that moves to solve the climate crisis could result in higher costs of living which would disproportionately affect those in already vulnerable circumstances adversely. Further, the COVID-19 pandemic showed us that protective isolation measures created loneliness and social issues especially for young people. The term highlights the systemic nature of

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contemporary global challenges and the need for holistic, multidisciplinary and lifelong approaches to crisis management and resolution.

In this article, we examine the implications of the polycrisis for health inequities and demonstrate that reducing these inequities is made increasingly complex by the interaction of multiple crises.

Polycrisis is above all a political crisis

Since 2000, there have been reversals in previous gains in terms of life expectancy in some countries and previously accepted rights such as reproductive rights. The world has experienced a global pandemic, growing inequities, environmental breakdown, multiple wars, financial crises, existential loneliness and social disconnection linked to the recent developments in ageing and territorial disparities, as well as a global refugee crisis. The period has also been marked by the undermining of policies and practices centred on inclusion and equity that many thought were established. Major global trends—including changes in planetary ecosystems, rapid advances in digital technologies, urbanisation, nutrition transition, globalised commercial interests, demographic changes, populism, energy poverty, war and conflict—bring both opportunities and the risk of increasing health inequalities.

The 2024 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) report notes that only 17% of the targets are on track.² At EU level, progress still needs to be made to reach the three EU headline targets proposed by the European Commission and agreed by the European Council to be achieved by 2030 in the areas of employment, skills, and social protection, consistent with the SDGs, and monitoring progress towards the ambitions and political commitment of the European Pillar of Social Rights*. Although the targets are within reach, concerns are mounting about countries' ability to face to the many crises which are negatively impacting poverty and inequalities.

The COVID-19 pandemic for instance tested the public health, social welfare systems and political systems of all countries³ and exposed many shortcomings. The pandemic also highlighted inequities both within and between countries, as seen in differential deaths rates.^{4,5} The frequency of pandemics like COVID-19 is predicted to increase.⁶ Since the pandemic, an inflation-driven cost of living crisis has pushed people into poverty^{7,8} and, in many places, has coincided with a housing affordability crisis.

An epidemic of non-communicable diseases is being fuelled by a food supply dominated by ultra processed foods, which have been shown to negatively affect both physical⁹ and mental health.¹⁰ Social media has many benefits but it also poses health risks, especially to younger people's mental health.^{11,12} Artificial intelligence presents new challenges and threatens to exacerbate unemployment and uncertainties.¹³

“rising
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Societies across Europe are witnessing rising polarisation and discrimination, threatening social cohesion. The direct and indirect impacts of climate change and environmental degradation on physical and mental health are increasing,¹² disproportionately affecting the most vulnerable communities, who often bear less responsibility for the causes of climate change but are least able to adapt.

Populist political parties are raising concerns about the extent of migration into Europe, leading to divisive policies¹⁴ that fail to address the root causes of migration or the colonial history underlying many of the problems. Competitiveness and security are emerging as key priorities in the new European political landscape, with health and wellbeing increasingly pushed to the sidelines, while at the same time we have multiple examples of the fact that robust social protection systems have been pivotal in addressing polycrises.¹⁵

Across Europe, people are grappling with these multiple challenges, resulting in growing uncertainty and insecurity. These adversities significantly impact individuals' health and wellbeing and create the conditions for persisting and worsening health inequalities. The 2022 Eurobarometer on social fairness showed that four out of five citizens in the EU think that inequalities in their countries are too high. At the root of these crises are unjust economic systems, where a small minority benefit while the majority face increasingly difficult living conditions. Tackling health inequities in the midst of polycrisis will require urgent, targeted action across many sectors, actors and levels.

The everyday living conditions that are favourable for health equity have been known for some time and are listed in Table 1. They were laid out in the 2008 report of the Commission on the Social Determinants of Health¹⁶ and their importance was acknowledged in the 1978 WHO Alma-Ata Declaration on Primary Health Care. The SDGs also acknowledge the importance of each of these areas. So, why hasn't the world acted? The knowledge is there, and the need is clear. Yet what is missing are concrete actions, visibly linked to the political will for action. How can we explain this lack of commitment in a world that has agreed on achieving the SDGs?

Taking action to improve health and reduce health inequalities

While everyday living conditions were a primary focus of the Commission on the Social Determinants of Health (CSDH), the fourth section addressed “Power, Money and Resources”. This section highlighted that it is the failure of governments and international agencies to address the structural factors that shape the social determinants of health, and are a key explanation for the regression in health equity.

A recent review¹⁷ of the structural determinants of health concluded that public health practice requires a greater focus on these structural elements, urging public health professionals to engage in power and politics. The lack of attention to the structural recommendations in the

* See the European Commission's web pages on the European Pillar of Social Rights. <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1226&langId=en>

Table 1: Everyday conditions of living for creating health equity

AREA	CONDITIONS
Early childhood	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making sure girls' and boys' first 1000 days are nurturing and supported • Providing free early childhood education and care, in particular for children in need • Providing free and effective access to healthcare • Providing free and effective access to at least one healthy meal per day and effective access to nutrition • Ensuring access to adequate housing
Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free, accessible education from early childhood to university, in particular to children and young people in need, paying attention to specific cohorts facing multiple challenges
Supportive environments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participatory local governance • Urban living conditions that are supportive of healthy lifestyles, conviviality, adapted to the needs of older people or persons with disabilities and promoting independent living (in line with the accessibility requirements) • Supportive rural areas to stem depopulation including land rights and support for rural livelihoods • Protection of natural environments including reducing carbon emissions • Ensuring access to social and essential services and sufficient skilled workforce
Fair employment and decent work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Representation of workers in governance of workplaces • Safe and decent work standards • Occupation health and safety applied to all workers, both formal and informal • Regulation to protect precarious workers • Social protection across the life-course, at a level that is sufficient for healthy living • Social protection coverage to include those in precarious work and informal care work, as well as flexible working conditions, including self-employed
Universal health care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building health systems based on comprehensive primary health care • Publicly funded universal system of tax/insurance-based system regardless of ability to pay and minimal out-of-pocket health spending • Measures to ensure adequate health professionals in rural areas • Health system sensitive to needs of all people including those with disabilities, Indigenous, women, and LGBTQI+

Source: authors' own.

CSDH report is an important reason for growing health inequities and declining life expectancies in some countries, especially after COVID-19.¹⁸

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So what would action on the structural determinants look like? We define eight critical areas for action.

1. Ensure planetary limits are not exceeded. The UN Secretary General¹⁹ recently made the point that staying within the 1.5 degree of planetary warming is not merely a goal or target but a critical limit. Beyond this threshold, climate change will not only worsen but also become unpredictable, with synergistic events creating

instabilities that are hard to predict. People with fewer protective resources are more vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, and as these impacts are felt inequities will grow. In addition, air pollution, as one of the most important environmental health risk factors, is linked to almost 400,000 deaths annually in the European Union²⁰ and over 4 million globally in 2019.²¹

2. Make sure no one is left behind. Equity needs to be a focus at all stages of policy design and implementation, ensuring that targeted measures and instruments are developed. For example, the only way we will successfully achieve climate goals is by ensuring that everyone has the capacity and opportunity to contribute, and that the green transition is a just transition. The health argument can be a powerful tool to get people on board. The Social Climate Fund,²⁰ for example, is a start, but much more is needed.

3. Foster co-creation to ensure communities and civil society collectively and cooperatively craft a vision of a better future. Inclusive, meaningful social participation can help to make sure everyone's voice is heard, including those who may not feel listened to. Involving people in decision-making processes contributes to shaping policies and actions that are more tailored to local needs. This can also help to build social cohesion, renew trust in government and institutions, and foster pro-environmental and health behaviours. Ensuring that civil society has the freedom to protest government decision is a vital aspect of ensuring inclusive policymaking. Yet in many countries CIVICUS²² has shown that democratic spaces are closing rather than opening, and that civil society action is often under threat.

4. Reduce wealth inequities as they drive health inequities. Wealth inequality remains high in Europe. In 2022, the wealth Gini co-efficient ranged from a high of 87.4 in Sweden to 5.08 in Slovakia.²³ Measures to reduce wealth inequities include inheritance taxes and wealth taxes, and more recently more radical solutions have been suggested, such as a cap on the wealth that any one person can hold. The wages of corporation's executive staff have become much higher as a ratio of the average wage over the past four decades. Studies show that wage disparity has significantly increased over time, with just a small dip during the COVID-19 pandemic: in the US CEOs were paid 344 times as much as a typical worker in 2022, up from a ratio of 21 to 1 in 1965.²⁴ While lower in Europe, the ratio was still 201 in the United Kingdom, 171 in The Netherlands, and 136 in Germany.²⁵ Measures could be instituted to reduce these disparities.

5. Ensure that welfare and social protection systems and public services are robust, equity-driven and prevention-led. Insufficient, inadequate and under-funded social protection and welfare systems cannot meet the growing needs of those impacted by the polycrisis we are facing. A holistic approach is needed to truly act on

the determinants of health and give everyone – regardless of age, gender, ethnicity, disability or socioeconomic status – the opportunity to improve their living conditions and lead healthy, fulfilling lives. As Europe’s population ages, ensuring accessible and high-quality long-term care is crucial for upholding dignity and social inclusion in later life. The European Pillar of Social Rights is a policy instrument and action plan that will be reviewed in the new European Commission mandate. By addressing structural determinants, the Pillar can be considered a European Pillar for Health Equity.²⁶

6. Constrain the power and influence of trans-national corporations (TNCs)

which has grown significantly in the last three decades. An analysis of the **commercial determinants of health** demonstrated the ways in which the global political economy works in the favour of TNCs.²⁷ This is shown by the way trade agreements favour these corporations, low taxation regimes and few international agreements exist which prevent tax avoidance practices effectively. Many practices of these corporations undermine health including manipulative marketing of unhealth products, distortion of science, tax evasion, extensive lobbying of government to achieve a corporate friendly public policy environment, externalising of harms they cause to government through the need for health care provision for harms from product and environmental damage.^{27–29}

7. Tighten regulation of asset management companies

to ensure that financial systems do not undermine, health, equity, and the environment. The increase in size and importance of a country’s financial sector relative to its overall economy is another driver of growing inequities. Friel et al.³⁰ note that capitalism changed again in the 21st century, with “large-scale profits now accrue predominantly through financial and intellectual property channels rather than through the production and consumption of real goods and services”. Asset management companies now make investments for short term profit across various

sectors including health, housing and care services. Research has shown that financialisation has increased inequality, slowed investment in ‘real’ production, added pressures on indebted households and individuals, and led to a decline in democratic accountability.^{31–33} The Global Financial Crisis was partly attributed to financialisation.

8. Focus on inclusion and equity

in education which are crucial determinants of health outcomes and social mobility. Educational disparities persist across Europe, with significant variations in access to quality education and educational attainment between socioeconomic groups. The PISA 2022 results³⁴ show that students from disadvantaged backgrounds consistently perform worse than their more advantaged peers, with some countries exhibiting larger gaps than others. Early childhood education and care (ECEC) participation rates also vary widely. These disparities in education contribute to perpetuating health inequities, as higher educational attainment is strongly associated with better health outcomes, health literacy, and access to health-promoting resources. Addressing educational inequities requires comprehensive policies that target both access and quality, including increased investment in public education, targeted support for disadvantaged students, improvement of ECEC provision, and measures to reduce school segregation. Additionally, integrating health education and promotion into school curricula can further enhance the role of education in improving population health. Efforts to create more inclusive and equitable education systems are essential for breaking intergenerational cycles of disadvantage and reducing health inequities across Europe.

Conclusions

The concept of a wellbeing economy³⁵ is helpful in the transformation towards fairer systems that prioritise people and planetary wellbeing over economic growth at all costs. Establishing such economies will require considerable change in national economic thinking and priorities,

and as yet, no country has undertaken such a radical transformation. Yet, coordinated improvements in health, education, social protection, redistribution and equality could create a virtuous circle in which wellbeing and a thriving economy are mutually reinforcing, ultimately leading to a reduction in health inequalities.

Further research is required to document the efforts nations are making to reduce inequities in a systematic and deliberate way. More capacity for advocacy and work towards ensuring a systemic approach – by addressing health equity in all policies – is needed as well. But political will for achieving health equity seems to be weak in Europe. The crucial question remains: how can this political will be generated?

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Historical examples indicate that social change happens when it is demanded by well-organised civil society movements. This was the case with the abolition of slavery in the nineteenth century, the women’s suffrage movement, desegregation in the United States, and the fight for marriage equality. Does Europe now need a social movement for health equity?

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